

VAQT BO'YICHA KASR TARTIBLI TO'LQIN TENGLAMASI UCHUN
BIR NOLOKAL MASALA HAQIDA

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7649026>

ELSEVIER

Received: 16-02-2023
Accepted: 17-02-2023
Published: 22-02-2023

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada vaqt o'zgaruvchisi bo'yicha umumlashgan Xilfer kasr tartibli operatori ishtirok etgan to'lqin tenglamasi uchun nolokal shartli chegaraviy masalaning bir qiymatli yechilishi tadqiq etilgan. Bunda o'zgaruvchilarni ajratish usuli hamda kasr tartibli tenglama uchun Koshi masalasini yechish usullaridan foydalanilgan.

Keywords: Xilfer kasr tartibli hosilasi; to'lqin tenglamasi; Koshi masalasi; Furiye usuli.

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ON A NONLOCAL PROBLEM FOR TIME-FRACTIONAL WAVE EQUATION

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Received: 16-02-2023
Accepted: 17-02-2023
Published: 22-02-2023

Abstract: In this paper, a unique solvability of a problem with nonlocal condition for the wave equation involving generalized Hilfer fractional derivative has been proved. The method of a separation of variables and the solution of the Cauchy problem are key tools of investigation.

Keywords: Hilfer fractional derivative; wave equation; Cauchy problem; Fourier method.

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ОБ ОДНОЙ НЕЛОКАЛЬНОЙ ЗАДАЧЕ ДЛЯ ВОЛНОВОГО УРАВНЕНИЯ
ДРОБНОГО ПОРЯДКА ПО ВРЕМЕНИ

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Received: 16-02-2023
Accepted: 17-02-2023
Published: 22-02-2023

Abstract: В этой статье доказана однозначная разрешимость задачи с нелокальными условиями для волнового уравнения с обобщенным дробным производным Хилфера. При этом использованы метод разделения переменных и решение задачи Коши.

Keywords: Дробное производное Хилфера; волновое уравнение; задача Коши; метод Фурье.

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Ma'lumki, xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalar fizika, mexanika, biologiya, kimyo va boshqa ko'plab amaliyotga bog'langan fanlardagi jarayonlarni matematik modellashtirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi [1-4]. Oxirgi yillarda bunday matematik modellarni mukkamallashtirishda kasr tartibli hosilalar qatnashgan turli xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalardan foydalanilyapti [5-6]. Bunga kasr tartibli analizning o'ziga xos usullari ishlab chiqilgani ham asos bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda [7-8]. Kasr tartibli hosilalar asosan vaqt o'zgaruvchisiga nisbatan qo'llanilayotganining ham o'ziga xos sabablari bo'lib, bu xotira effekti, g'ovak muhitlar bilan bog'liqdir [9]. Kasr tartibli hosilalarning ham turli tiplari kiritilgan bo'lib [10], ularning strukturasi qarab turli maqsadlarda foydalanilyapti. Ushbu ishda qo'llanilgan umumlashgan Xilfer kasr tartibli hosilasi dastlab [11] ishda kiritilib o'rganilgan bo'lishiga qaramasdan, bu hosilani avvalroq kiritilgan, lekin ko'pchilikka ma'lum bo'lmagan Jrbashyan-Nersesyan operatorining xususiy holi sifatida olish mumkin [12].

Quyidagi

$$D_{ot}^{(a,b)m}u(x,y,t) = U_{xx}(x,y,t) + U_{yy}(x,y,t) \quad (1)$$

tenglamani $W = \{(x,y,t) : 0 < t < T, 0 < x < 1, 0 < y < 1\}$ sohada tadqiq etamiz. Bu yerda a, b -shunday haqiqiy sonlarki, $1 < a, b \leq 2$ va

$$D_{ot}^{(a,b)}f(t) = I_{ot}^{m(2-a)} \frac{d}{dt} I_{ot}^{(1-m)(2-b)} f(t) \quad (2)$$

a, b tartibli, $m \in [0, 1]$ tipdagi umumlashgan Xilfer kasr tartibli operator [11],

I_{ot}^j esa

$$I_{ot}^j f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(j)} \int_0^t (t-z)^{j-1} f(z) dz, t > 0 \quad (3)$$

formula bilan aniqlanuvchi j -tartibli Riman-Liuuill integral operatori [7].

(1) tenglama uchun W sohada quyidagi masalani taqdim etamiz:

Masala. (1) tenglamaning W sohadagi quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi regulyar yechimi topilsin:

$$u(0,y,t) = 0, u(1,y,t) = 0 \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, 0 < t \leq T, \quad (4)$$

$$u(x,0,t) = 0, u(x,1,t) = 0 \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, 0 < t \leq T, \quad (5)$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} I_{ot}^{(1-m)(1-b)} u(x,y,t) = u(x,y,x) + j(x,y), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad 0 < x \leq T \quad (6)$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{d}{dt} I_{ot}^{(1-m)(2-b)} u(x,y,t) = y(x,y), \quad 0 < x < 1, \quad 0 < y < 1, \quad (7)$$

Bu yerda $j(x,y), y(x,y)$ - berilgan funksiyalar.

Ta'rif. (1) tenglamaning W sohadagi **regulyar yechimi** deb shunday $u(x, y, t)$, funksiyaga aytiladiki u

$$D_{0t}^{(a,b)m} u(x, y, t) \in C(W), u_{xx}(x, y, t), u_{yy}(x, y, t) \in C(W), t^{(1-m)(2-b)} u(x, y, t) \in C(\bar{W})$$

regulyarlik shartlarini hamda W sohada (1) tenglamani qanoatlantiradi.

Masalani o'zgaruvchilarni ajratish usuli bilan tadqiq etamiz. Bunda masala yechimi

$$u(x, y, t) = \sum_{m,n=0}^{\infty} U_{m,n}(t) \sin(np x) \sin(mp y) \quad (8)$$

ko'rinishda qidiriladi, bu yerda $U_{m,n}(t)$ noma'lum funksiyalar bo'lib, ularni topish uchun keyinchalik mos nolokal shartli masalaga kelinadi. Buning uchun (8) ni (1) tenglamaga va (6), (7) boshlang'ich shartlarga qo'yamiz va t o'zgaruvchiga nisbatan quyidagi nolokal masalani olamiz:

$$\begin{cases} D_{0t}^{(a,b)m} U_{m,n}(t) + m_{m,n} U_{m,n}(t) = 0, \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} I_{0t}^{(1-m)(1-b)} U_{m,n}(t) = U_{m,n}(x) + j_{m,n}, \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{d}{dt} I_{0t}^{(1-m)(1-b)} U_{m,n}(t) = y_{m,n}. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Bu yerda $m_{m,n} = (np)^2 + (mp)^2$, $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, $j_{m,n}$ va $y_{m,n}$ lar esa mos ravishda $j(x, y)$ va $y(x, y)$ funksiyalarning Furye koeffitsiyentlaridir.

Kasr tartibli hosilalar ishtirok etgan to'liq tenglamalari uchun masalalar [13-14] ishlarda ham tadqiq etilgan.

Agar $U_{m,n}(x)$ ni vaqtincha ma'lum deb tursak, (9) masalaning yechimi dastlab

$$U_{m,n}(t) = \check{U}_{m,n}(x) + j_{m,n} \frac{\Gamma^{g-1} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} t^d)}{\Gamma} + y_{m,n} t^{g-2} E_{d,g-1}(-m_{m,n} t^d) \quad (10)$$

ko'rinishida yoziladi. Bu yerda

$$g = b + m(2 - b), d = b + m(a - b), E_{a,b}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(ak + b)}$$

ikki karrali Mittag-Leffler funksiyasi [8].

(10) da $t = x$ desak

$$U_{m,n}(x) = \check{U}_{m,n}(x) + j_{m,n} \frac{\Gamma^{g-1} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} x^g)}{\Gamma} + y_{m,n} x^{g-2} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} x^g)$$

hosil bo'ladi. Bu yerda esa $U_{m,n}(x)$ ni quyidagicha topamiz:

$$U_{m,n}(x) = \frac{1}{1 - x^{g-1} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} x^d)} j_{m,n} x^{g-2} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} x^d) + y_{m,n} x^{g-2} E_{d,g-1}(-m_{m,n} x^d) \quad (11)$$

Ta'kidlash kerakki, $x \geq 0$ bo'lgani uchun $1 - x^{g-1} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} x^d) \geq 0$ barcha $d, g, m_{m,n}$ lar uchun bajariladi. Demak, (11) ni hisobga olib (10) ni quyidagicha yozib olish mumkin:

$$U_{m,n}(t) = \frac{j_{m,n} t^{g-1} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} t^d) + y_{m,n} t^{g-2} E_{d,g-1}(-m_{m,n} t^d) + j_{m,n} x^{g-1} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} x^d) + y_{m,n} x^{g-2} E_{d,g-1}(-m_{m,n} x^d)}{1 - x^{g-1} E_{d,g}(-m_{m,n} x^d)} \quad (12)$$

(8) formula bilan berilgan cheksiz qatorning tekisi yaqinlashishini isbotlash uchun $U_{m,n}(t)$ baholab olamiz. Buning uchun

$$\left| E_{a,b}(z) \right| \leq \frac{c}{1 + |z|} \quad (13)$$

bahodan foydalanamiz [8].

$$\left| U_{m,n}(t) \right| \leq |j_{m,n}| \frac{t^{g-1}}{1 + |m_{m,n} t^d|} + |y_{m,n}| \frac{c t^{g-2}}{1 + |m_{m,n} t^d|} + |j_{m,n}| \frac{c |x^{g-1}|}{1 + |m_{m,n} x^d|} + |y_{m,n}| \frac{c |x^{g-2}|}{1 + |m_{m,n} x^d|}$$

yoki

$$\left| U_{m,n}(t) \right| \leq \frac{c_1}{|m_{m,n}|} \frac{|j_{m,n}|}{|t^{d+1-g}|} + \frac{c_2}{|m_{m,n}|} \frac{|y_{m,n}|}{|t^{d+2-g}|} \quad (14)$$

(14) ni hisobga olsak (8) dan

$$\left| u(x,y,t) \right| \leq \sum_{m,n=0}^{\infty} \frac{|j_{m,n}|}{|m_{m,n}|} \frac{c_1}{|t^{d+1-g}|} + \frac{|y_{m,n}|}{|m_{m,n}|} \frac{c_2}{|t^{d+2-g}|} \quad (15)$$

ni olish mumkin. $u_{xx}(x,y,t)$, $u_{yy}(x,y,t)$ funksiyalarga mos keluvchi cheksiz qatorlar uchun

$$\left| u_{xx}(x,y,t) \right| \leq \sum_{m,n=0}^{\infty} \frac{c_3}{|m_{m,n}|} \frac{|j_{m,n}|}{|t^{d+1-g}|} + \frac{c_4}{|m_{m,n}|} |y_{m,n}|$$

$$\left| u_{yy}(x,y,t) \right| \leq \sum_{m,n=0}^{\infty} \frac{c_3}{|m_{m,n}|} \frac{|j_{m,n}|}{|t^{d+1-g}|} + \frac{c_4}{|m_{m,n}|} |y_{m,n}| \quad (16)$$

baho kerak bo'lad. (15) va (16) da Parseval tenglidan foydalansak [1]

$$\left\| u(x,y,t) \right\|_2^2 \leq c_5 + \|j\|_2^2 + \|y\|_2^2, \quad \left\| u_{xx}(x,y,t) \right\|_2^2 \leq c_6 + \|j'_x\|_2^2 + \|y'_x\|_2^2,$$

$$\|u_{yy}(x,y,t)\|_J c_7 + \|j'_y\|_2^2 + \|y'_y\|_2^2 \quad (17)$$

ni olamiz. Bu esa $u(x,y,t)$ va $u_{xx}(x,y,t)$ funksiyalarga mos keluvchi cheksiz qatorlarning tekis yaqinlashishini isbotlaydi.

Masala yechimining yagonaligi fazoviy o'zgaruvchilar bo'yicha olingan sistemalarning to'la ortonormal basis tashkil etishidan kelib chiqadi. Demak, quyidagi tasdiq o'rinli:

Teorema. Agar

$$\varphi(x,y), \psi(x,y) \in C([0,1] \times [0,1]),$$

$$\varphi_x(x,y), \psi_x(x,y) \in L_2((0,1) \times (0,1)), \varphi_y(x,y), \psi_y(x,y) \in L_2((0,1) \times (0,1))$$

bo'lsa, u holda masala yagona yechimga ega va u (8) ko'rinishda topiladi.

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